

Spectrophotometric Study of Vo(II) Complex of Quinizarin-2-Sulphonic Acid

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In continuation of our work on complexes of β -resorcylic acid (abbreviated as β -RA) with $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})^+$ ion, it is observed that $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ ion with β -RA forms a water soluble, green complex, in the ratio 1 : 1 at pH 5.0.

β -RA used is of B.D.H. 'L.R.' and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ of B.D.H. 'Analar' quality. For buffer solutions, electrolyte solutions, instruments and chemicals, the experimental setup and the procedure are the same as in our previous communications.^{2,3} The pH is adjusted by buffering 10 ml. of the mixed solutions with 2 ml. of the required buffer.

Application of the method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁴ to the system CuSO_4 - β -RA (in the ratio 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 2 : 1 Cu^{2+} to β -RA) keeping total volume 12 ml. and pH 5.0 demonstrates the formation of one complex having λ_{max} at 385 $\text{m}\mu$ under these experimental conditions. The reactants have negligible absorbance at the chosen wave lengths 390 $\text{m}\mu$ and 400 $\text{m}\mu$.

Absorbance (both at 390 $\text{m}\mu$ and 400 $\text{m}\mu$) of solutions containing CuSO_4 and β -RA (1 : 1) increases upto pH 4.76 and then decreases. Application of Job's method of continued variations⁵ to the system CuSO_4 - β -RA, keeping total volume 12 ml (10 ml CuSO_4 + β -RA and 2 ml. of the required buffer), shows that 1 : 1 complex is formed between pH 4.76 and 5.37.

The 1 : 1 ratio of the complex has also been established spectrophotometrically using the mole-ratio method⁶ and slope-ratio method.⁷

Log K value of the complex, evaluated by mole-ratio method is 3.0 at 27°. Molar extinction coefficient of the complex, determined by slope-ratio method at pH 5, is 39.8 at 390 $\text{m}\mu$ and 37 at 400 $\text{m}\mu$.

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